

THE CONCEPT OF CASE STUDY METHOD IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

People encounter the reality that willpower is insufficient when learning a foreign language. It is imperative that you select a training approach based on your needs and goals. A key factor in the effective acquisition of a foreign language is the teacher. This article emphasizes the examination of the particular scenario put forth by the teacher along with supplementary resources, creation of the best possible solution, and presentation of this issue to a skilled audience when teaching foreign languages.

Key words: *social skills, problem-solving skills, qualitative changes, creative thinking, critical thinking, responsible, facilitate, data network*

Improving the quality and accessibility of education is the primary goal of education system reforms, which are necessary to alter the socioeconomic and political environments that shape society's progress. Additionally, there is a need to improve academic mobility, fortify ties between various educational institutions and levels of education, and resolve the issues surrounding the integration education into the contemporary scientific and educational sphere. The process of improving technical means of information transmission, developing computer and telecommunications networks, and introducing new educational information technologies all contribute to the "informatization" of the educational system, which is required for qualitative changes in the educational system.

Technology as a science has the primary responsibility of determining the best teaching strategies for future real-world implementation. In the shortest amount of time and with the fewest financial and intellectual expenses, the effectiveness of the selected teaching strategies should be attained. These novel approaches, tactics, and forms in the fields of education and training—that is, innovations or innovative technologies—are examples of such successful strategies. With the use of cutting-edge educational technologies, students can better prepare for adulthood, become self-sufficient in navigating the demands of contemporary society, develop new

personal traits like unconventional problem-solving skills and creative thinking, and realize their full potential.

The education system's alignment with contemporary socio-economic and political demands is facilitated not only by structural and organizational innovations but also by the utilization of new technologies in staff training and substantial modifications to the educational process's content system. The challenge of implementing new, qualitative changes in the educational system is successfully resolved by the introduction of new information and communication technologies that can store, process, and transmit information. The adoption of interactive teaching methods and real-time technologies necessitates substantial telecommunications resources that can facilitate the necessary interconnection of learners, support multimedia technologies, ensure high-performance telecommunications equipment, and facilitate data network data transfer throughput.

Even so, the teacher is still responsible for implementing the majority of pedagogical functions despite the wide range of instructional technologies available, including computer, problem-based, didactic, modular, and others. Teachers are becoming more adept at performing the roles of advisor, consultant, and instructor as a result of the integration of contemporary technologies into the classroom. Since teaching is a specialized profession, it calls for specialized psychological and pedagogical training in addition to up-to-date information in the fields of pedagogy and psychology and technological training. based on this, openness to observing, assessing, and applying educational innovations.

The broad use of information and educational space is the foundation of the modern method to teaching foreign languages. This is when innovative educational models, pedagogical innovations, technologies, and approaches outperform old teaching methods. One of these is a brand-new approach to training arrangements known as the situation analysis or case study method. First implemented in 1924, this approach was created by the Harvard Business School in the United States. These days, there are two traditional case-study universities: Manchester (European) and Harvard (American). While the Manchester School's creators are thinking about a multi-variant answer to the problem, American researchers think that the goal of this strategy is to uncover the one accurate option. The Case-Study technique was effectively applied in practice by Dr. Copeland, J.A. Erskine, and M.R. Leenders, three American educators. The late 1990s saw the introduction of the Case-Study approach, which was preceded by educational reforms and the active adoption of interactive teaching techniques.

The CASE STUDY approach encourages the growth of a variety of abilities:

1. "Skills in analysis.

These comprise the following: the capacity to discern between data and information, categorize, emphasize important and irrelevant information, evaluate, display, and extract it, as well as identify information gaps and be able to fill them. Think rationally and with clarity. This is particularly crucial in cases where the quality of the information is low.

2. Useful abilities.

The case study's challenge is less complex than the actual scenario, which helps practitioners develop their ability to apply economic theory, methodologies, and principles.

3. Creative skills.

Usually, CASE logic is insufficient to resolve the issue on its own. When coming up with alternate answers that defy logic, creative thinking is crucial.

4. Communication skills.

Among these are the following: the capacity to guide a conversation and persuade people. Utilize visual materials and other media tools, collaborate with others in groups, stand up for your beliefs, persuade opponents, and compose a succinct, compelling report.

5. Social skills.

Certain social skills are formed throughout the CASE conversation, such as evaluating other people's conduct, listening, offering support during a discussion or countering an opposing viewpoint, self-control, etc.

6. Introspection.

In a discussion, disagreement encourages knowledge and study of one's own and other people's viewpoints. To address new moral and ethical issues, social skills development is necessary. Using the case approach, students and teachers actively engage in discussing solutions to a range of scenarios as well as particular issues or cases. However, it's also critical to remember that the scenario or instance under analysis is real and has a problem that needs to be fixed. [Smolyaninova,2000]

In turn, the problem under discussion has particular facts and consistent features. As a result, the classroom becomes an actual practical setting that motivates students to come up with a well-reasoned solution to a problem that arises in real life. Cases can be presented in paper, as written accounts of actual people's experiences, as multimedia, or through video. A case's volume might vary greatly, from a few lines on a single page to multiple pages detailing one or more occurrences. According to V. Davidenko, case assignments fall into three categories:

- huge unstructured cases (up to 50 pages with detailed information);
- "small sketches" cases (1–10 pages of text and 1-2 pages of extra material with essential concepts);

- organized cases (minimal information, optimal solution). The student's job is to specifically draw attention to the data that is essential for situation analysis;

"Pioneering cases" (in which students gain new theoretical and practical abilities in addition to updating the studied educational material).

Every case is predicated on an issue, incident, or dispute involving members of various social groupings who are situated within a certain temporal context. Students must evaluate this actual scenario, revise previously finished course materials, and create a detailed action plan in order to address the suggested issue. Students must "get into character" and put themselves in the shoes of one of the case's players in order to visualize the suggested scenario clearly. In this instance, in order to portray the participant's job as exactly as possible, they will need to examine his personality traits. The case method works best when teaching professional communication in a foreign language, such as when teaching business languages or languages for technologists, engineers, economists, and other professionals. This is because it fosters the development of communicative competence, both linguistic and sociocultural, and forms a number of professional qualities that are essential for future employment.

The matter is managed phase-by-phase:

Step 1: Familiarization with the Case: Students work independently on their own to become familiar with the case material. This often entails reading and then translating into Russian an original or partially altered document with a professional orientation, where the task in the specialty is articulated;

Stage 2 entails updating the internal monologue in a foreign language and requires searching independently for a solution or working in small groups to identify the sole agreed-upon answer to the challenging issue;

Stage 3: In class, students propose and defend the produced answer to the problem through prepared or impromptu monologues and dialogic speeches in a foreign language.

Consequently, discourse in a foreign language takes place in the following order: a review of the data received and included in the case, emphasizing the most crucial data; discussion and creation of a work plan to address the issue; addressing a problem (talk); creating a fix for the issue; debate in order to reach a decision; putting together a report; In a well-reasoned brief report, O.G. Smolyaninova suggests six formats for the problem-solving discussion process within the context of the study of the didactic possibilities of the case method:[Fedyanin,2000]

1. "Teacher-student: Interrogation in tandem. Talk between you and the instructor. A set of questions will be used to evaluate your remark, stance, or

suggestion. Do a thorough investigation because the reasoning behind your claims will be shown, so proceed with caution.

2. Devil's advocate between teacher and student. Usually, just you and the teacher are having this conversation, but occasionally, other students might as well. The teacher assumes a role that is wholly inappropriate for defense and asks you and possibly other people to act as attorneys. You should actively reason, put data in a specific sequence, apply concepts or theories, and draw from your own experiences.

3. The hypothetical format between the teacher and the student. Like the last one, but with one exception: the instructor will pose a fictitious scenario that is outside the purview of your advice or stance. We'll want you to assess this fictitious circumstance. You have to be willing to consider changing their perspective at any point during the conversation.

4. Student-student interaction: collaboration or confrontation. Students engage in debate with one another in this approach. There is a tendency toward both cooperation and antagonism. For instance, a student might refute your assertions by supplying fresh data. One student or you will attempt to "fend off the challenge." You will be able to learn more through cooperative behavior and constructive conflict resolution (as opposed to individual efforts).

5. Student - student: “Play a role.” Your teacher can urge you to adopt a role and engage with your peers in that capacity.

6. Instructor-student: "Quiet" style. An issue that was initially addressed to one student may be brought up by the teacher and later to the entire class.

The case method in training adjusts future specialists to real world scenarios and develops active skills in making decisions on diverse professional difficulties. This method is currently commonly utilized for testing residual knowledge as well as for monitoring finished educational material during the process of acquiring new knowledge. Exams dubbed "case" are getting more and more common; in these, students are required to examine a case and determine the one and only right answer, either orally or digitally. Here is an instance of a case task like this:

Select the replica that works best in the given communication scenario:

Receptionist: "Please give me a moment while I check." For tonight, you have a three-room suite or a reservation.

Visitor: « _____ »

1. I must be mistaken. Not that I need a suite.
2. What? You weren't asked for a suite by me.
3. I'll reserve a room here.
4. I fear that something went wrong. I didn't want a suite; I only wanted a single room.

In conclusion, there are acknowledged benefits and drawbacks to each strategy. The development of students' professional and communication competence, their ability to adapt to future professional activities, their growth of cognitive and creative skills, and their ability to make decisions are some of the case method's primary benefits. When teaching a foreign language at a university, the application of the case method boosts students' willingness to learn and become proficient with computers and the Internet's information area. The primary drawback of this training arrangement is that there is no assurance that each student will be able to finish every assignment on their own. When using the case method, foreign language teachers must possess exceptional pedagogical abilities, excellent qualifications, and a readiness to commit significant time and resources to being ready for work in this mode. This may involve consulting with colleagues who teach specialized topics. The primary responsibilities of the teacher in the classroom are to facilitate group discussions, push students to give up on narrow thinking, and include every member of the class in the case analysis process.[Surmina,2002]

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